

Light is Gravity – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework which regard bosonic propagations as net curvature on a varying Lorenz manifold, (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$, invoked stationary, and the recent result given by the coupling constant series. it is possible to construct the gravitational effect as a result of photons interacting with matter. As photons are propagating to long range while gravity is propagating to a short range due to its spin, a new picture now manifested.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.12)$$

Since according to modern theories of physics, the graviton particle has spin two, we can use the second representation of the coupling constant equation, i.e. spin representation using the prime critical line:

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (1.3)$$

$$\left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow [(2N(g)) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \quad (1.31)$$

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow 2N(g) \quad (1.31)$$

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow (1)$$

Recall that even amount of primes combined will never form a prime but an even number. The main point than is that even amount of variations vanish in this framework, and therefore the graviton will not propagate as spin one particle all across the matric. The propagation would be like the propagation of the strong interaction, as both have only one term in the coupling constants series. however, the photon propagating is adding up to a positive summation, each bosonic of the electric is $N_V = (+5)$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i > 0 \quad (1.32)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.33)$$

In addition, fermion clusters are demanded to vanish by stationary Lorenztion

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g}\right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'}\right] \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.34)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.35)$$

Since gravity is propagated as a short-range field, it cannot mediate the interaction at a long range, between fermion clusters, such as the earth and the sun. The photons are net curvature on the manifold, given by the coupling constant equation, and thus they are mediating the gravitational effect in quantum scale and it in agreement with the similarity between the structures of both interactions. Moreover, it is all given by just two equations, highly powerful equations.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)